

Supporting Information for Cellulose-Assisted Formation of 2D Hybrid Halide Perovskite Nanocrystals with Enhanced Stability for Light-Emitting Devices

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Experimental Section

Starting Materials: Lead iodide (PbI₂, 99%), methylammonium iodide (MAI, 98%), *n*-butylammonium iodide (BAI, 99%), titanium diisopropoxide bis(acetylacetonate) solution (75% in 2-propanol), spiro-MeOTAD, 4-*tert*-butylpyridine (TBP), lithium bis(trifluoromethylsulfonyl) imide (LiTFSI), cobalt (III) FK209 TFSI [6,6]-Phenyl C₆₁ butyric acid methyl ester (PCBM), poly(9-vinylcarbazole) (PVK), 2,2',2''-(1,3,5-Benzinetriyl)-tris(1-phenyl-1-*H*-benzimidazole) (TPBi), Poly(3,4-ethylenedioxythiophene)-poly(styrenesulfonate) (PEDOT:PSS), toluene (99.8) and acetonitrile (ACN, 99.9%) were supplied by Sigma-Aldrich. *N,N*-dimethylformamide (DMF, 99.8%) extra dry over Molecular Sieve, AcroSeal, and chlorobenzene extra dry over Molecular Sieve, AcroSeal were purchased from Acros Organics. Pure microcrystalline cellulose (Avicel PH200) was obtained from FMC Biopolymer. Aquivion® PW98 was purchased from Solvay Specialty Polymers and used without further treatment. Ultrapure water used was produced by a Millipore Milli-Q unit and pre-treated by a Millipore reverse osmosis system (>18.2 MΩ cm⁻¹).

The glass patterned with fluorine tin oxide (FTO) or indium tin oxide (ITO) were supplied by Pilkington. For the cleaning process, ethanol absolute dry (maximum 0.02% water) and isopropyl alcohol (technical grade, 99.5%) were purchased from PanReac and soap (decon90) from Decon.

Cellulose oligosaccharide (COS): The cellulose oligosaccharide was obtained following a mechanocatalytic approach. Microcrystalline cellulose (MCC, 20g) was mixed with an acid catalyst, Aquivion® PW98 (2 g), in a planetary ball mill (Retsch MP 100) in the presence of 20 Zirconium Oxide balls of 10mm, the same material as the bowl. The milling process was carried out at 400 rpm for 24 h.

The obtained mixture was dispersed in distilled water (20 mL water for each 300 mg of solid mixture), stirred, left in an ultrasonic bath for 2 h, and filtered through a 0.22 μm PTFE filter. The filtrate was lyophilized to give a pure yellowish-white cellulose oligosaccharide powder. Ultimately, Flash Column Chromatography (FP ID Si column, and 20 mL/min acetonitrile/water in a 10-80 wt% gradient) was used to obtain the final cellulose oligosaccharide. \bar{D} (SEC) = 1.09; \overline{DP}_n = 4 (NMR), M_n = 667 g/mol (NMR). (Figure 1).

Figure S1: $^1\text{H-NMR}$ (400 MHz, D_2O) spectrum of COS.

Substrate Preparation: All substrates were cleaned by a sequential sonication treatment in Decon 90, Milli-Q water, ethanol, and isopropyl alcohol, followed by ultraviolet-ozone treatment for 15 min.

Perovskite precursor solution: Stoichiometric precursor solutions were prepared by mixing PbI_2 , MAI, and BAI, in 0.5 mL of DMF following the steps detailed in previous works.^[1,2] Different concentrations of COS (1, 5, 10, 25, 50 and 75 mg/mL) were added to the perovskite solution and stirred around 30 min.

Perovskite Deposition: The perovskite films were deposited by the hot casting (HC) method.^[1,2] The substrates were heated at 90°C for 10 min. Then, they were moved quickly on the spin coater and $50 \mu\text{L}$ of the precursor solution was deposited on the substrates at 5000 rpm for 30 s. Finally, the films were annealed at 100°C for 20 min on a hot plate.

Perovskite light emitting devices (PeLEDs): The structure device given ITO/PEDOT:PSS/PVK/perovskite/TBPI/Al was fabricated. A PEDOT:PSS layer (40 nm in thickness) was deposited onto the ITO glass substrate by spin-coating (5000 rpm for 50 s) using 200 μ L of solution. Then, PEDOT:PSS layer was kept at 145 $^{\circ}$ C for 15 min. Later, PVK layer (40 nm) was synthesized using a toluene solution (10 mg in 1 mL). 100 μ L of PVK solution was deposited onto the PEDOT:PSS layer by spin-coating (3000 rpm, 60 s) and annealed at 140 $^{\circ}$ C for 30 min. The perovskite films (with or without COS) were deposited by the HC method as indicated above. After this, TBPI was spin coated at 5000 rpm, for 60 s from a toluene solution (10 mg in 1 mL) and annealed for 10 min at 100 $^{\circ}$ C. Finally, a 40 nm aluminium electrode was deposited as a metallic contact by thermal evaporation (1×10^{-6} torr.).

Electron-only Devices: The structure device given FTO/c-TiO₂/perovskite/PCBM/Au was fabricated.^[3] A compact blocking layer of TiO₂ (c-TiO₂, 30 nm in thickness) was deposited onto the FTO glass substrate by spray pyrolysis, using a titanium diisopropoxide bis(acetylacetonate) solution in ethanol (60% v/v). Then, c-TiO₂ layer was kept at 450 $^{\circ}$ C for 30 min for the formation of the anatase phase.^[4] Perovskite layers (with and without COS) have been deposited following the steps detailed above. 10 mg/mL PCBM chlorobenzene solution was spin-coated on perovskite films. After this, the films were annealed at 100 $^{\circ}$ C for 10 min. Then, a 40 nm gold electrode was deposited by thermal evaporation (1×10^{-6} torr.).

Hole-only Devices: The structure device given FTO/PEDOT:PSS/perovskite/spiro/Ag was fabricated. PEDOT:PSS and perovskite layers (with and without COS) were deposited as indicated above. After this, spiro-OMeTAD was spin-coated at 400 rpm for 20 s from a chlorobenzene solution (28.9 mg in 400 μ L) containing LiTFSI (7 μ L from a 520 mg/mL stock solution in acetonitrile), TBP (11.5 mL), and Co (III)TFSI (8.8 MI from a 40 mg/mL stock solution) as dopants.^[5] Finally, a 40 nm gold electrode was deposited by thermal evaporation (1×10^{-6} torr.).

X-ray Diffraction (XRD) Measurements: XRD experiments for all of samples were performed using a Bruker D8 DISCOVER diffractometer operating at 40 kV and 40 mA and using Cu K α radiation (1.54060 Å). The measurements were done from 2 to 40° Bragg angles.

Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM) Studies: SEM images of the samples were performed using a JEOL JSM 7800F microscope working at 2 kV. The work distances and magnification were \approx 3.7 mm and 20000 \times , respectively.

UV-Vis Absorption Spectroscopy: The measurement of the films was performed at room temperature (\approx 25 °C) using a Cary 100 UV–VIS spectrophotometer in the range of 500–800 nm in all cases.

Steady-State and Time-Resolved PL Measurements: Steady-state photoluminescence spectra were recorded with a FLS980 (Edinburgh Instruments) photoluminescence spectrometer using a 450 W Xenon arc lamp and a R298P photomultiplier as detector. Time-resolved fluorescence measurements were accomplished through the time-correlated single photon counting (TCSPC) technique, by using the same FLS980 (Edinburgh Instruments) photoluminescence spectrometer. The thin films were excited at 406.4 nm with an 86.8 ps pulse width diode laser using an R2658P photomultiplier as the detector. Temperature dependence PL measurements were carried out using an Optistat DN cryostat from Oxford instruments.

PL Quantum Yield Measurements: The PLQYs were measured using an integrating sphere coupled to an FLS980 photoluminescence spectrometer. The FLS980 was equipped with double monochromators, a 450 W Xenon lamp and a PMT-R2658P detector. A neutral density filter (OD = 3) was placed in the emission path to measure excitation region of the spectrum without detector saturation effects.

Transient Absorption Measurements: Femtosecond transient absorption measurements were performed using a broadband pump-probe transient absorption spectrometer (HELIOS, Ultrafast Systems). The pump light was

generated using a regenerative Ti:sapphire amplifier (Spitfire Ace, Spectra Physics, 1 kHz) that provides ultrashort pulses of high power at 800 nm. This system requires a seed laser to provide the input pulses and a pump laser to energize the amplifier. The regenerative amplifier is seeded using a Ti:sapphire femtosecond laser (MaiTai SP, Spectra Physics, 80 MHz) and pumped by a diodepumped Q-switched laser of Nd:YLF (Empower 45, Spectra Physics, 1 kHz). The amplified radiation (800 nm, 100 fs, 5W) is divided into two beams. The first one is used to pump a tunable optical parametric amplifier (TOPAS prime, Spectra Physics) in the range 290–1600 nm that generates the excitation of the sample and the second one is employed to generate white light for the absorption of the sample. In the Helios spectrometer, the UV–vis white light continuum generated by focusing the fundamental light from the amplifier on a thin CaF₂ crystal after the controlled optical delay (3.3 ns), was used as a probe beam, directed to the sample, and detected with a CMOS sensor. The pump pulse was chopped by a mechanical chopper synchronized to one-half of the laser repetition rate, resulting in a pair of the spectra, with and without the pump, from which the absorption change induced by the pump pulse was estimated.

X-Ray Photoelectron Spectroscopy: XPS measurements were taken on a Physical Electronics PHI 5700 spectrometer. Survey scans were acquired averaging two measurements with 200 eV pass energy and 1 eV energy step size. Elemental scans were acquired using 50 eV pass energy and 0.1 eV energy step size. 5 scans were used for Pb, 15 for C, 10 for N, and 4 for I.

Fourier-Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FTIR) Spectroscopy: The FTIR spectroscopy analysis was realized using an FTIR–ATR spectrometer PerkinElmer Spectrum Two. The spectrum was analyzed in the range of 2800–3600 cm⁻¹ with a resolution of 4 cm⁻¹, and a total of 40 scans were collected.

Device Characterization: Current–voltage curves were measured with a Keithley 2400 potentiostat. The PeLEDs and single carrier devices were masked with a metal aperture of 0.09 cm² to define the active area. The used photodiode to measure the photocurrent is Model 818 SL from Newport.

Synchrotron-based Grazing Incidence Wide Angle X-ray Scattering (GIWAXS): GIWAXS data were collected at NCD-SWEET beamline (ALBA synchrotron in Cerdanyola del Vallès, Spain). An X-ray beam produced by an in vacuo undulator was monochromatized using a Si (111) channel cut monochromator at 12.4 keV ($\lambda = 0.9998 \text{ \AA}$). The X-ray beam was also collimated with an array of Be lenses, obtaining a beam size at the sample position of $150 \times 50 \mu\text{m}^2$ [H \times V]. The 2D images were recorded with a Rayonix® LX255-HS area detector. The detector to sample distance, tilts, and reciprocal q-space were calibrated using Cr_2O_3 as standard, being the detector at 233.73 mm from the sample position. Data were analyzed using a homemade Python routine.

Figure S2. Change in the crystallite size of the 2D RP perovskites upon the addition of different percentages of the COS compound. The values are obtained from the Scherrer equation that relates the FWHM of the XRD peaks with the size of the crystallites.

Figure S3. FTIR spectra of the COS compound in a film and the $\text{BA}_2\text{MA}_4\text{Pb}_5\text{I}_{16}$ 2D RP perovskite film containing different amounts of the cellulose polymer in the initial precursor solution: 0 mg/mL, 10 mg/mL, 50 mg/mL, and 75 mg/mL.

Figure S4. Normalized photoluminescence spectra (A) and magnification of the high energy region of the PL spectra (B) of the $\text{BA}_2\text{MA}_4\text{Pb}_5\text{I}_{16}$ 2D RP perovskite films containing different amount of the cellulose polymer in the initial precursor solution: 0 mg/mL, 1 mg/mL, 5 mg/mL, 10 mg/mL, 25 mg/mL, 50 mg/mL and 75 mg/mL.

Figure S5. Dark J - V curves for electron-only devices of the $\text{BA}_2\text{MA}_4\text{Pb}_5\text{I}_{16}$ 2D RP perovskite films containing 10 mg/mL (a) and 50 mg/mL (b) of the cellulose oligosaccharide.

Figure S6. Dark J - V curves for hole-only devices of the $\text{BA}_2\text{MA}_4\text{Pb}_5\text{I}_{16}$ 2D RP perovskite films containing 0 mg/mL (A), 10 mg/mL (B), 50 mg/mL (C), and 75 mg/mL (D) of the cellulose oligosaccharide.

Figure S7. Transient absorption spectra at different delay times of the BA₂MA₄Pb₅I₁₆ 2D RP perovskite films containing 0 mg/mL (A), 25 mg/mL (B), 50 mg/mL (C) and 75 mg/mL (D) of the cellulose polymer. $\lambda_{\text{exc}} = 400$ nm.

Figure S8. Transient absorption time decays at $\lambda_{\text{probe}} = 610$ and 730 nm of the $\text{BA}_2\text{MA}_4\text{Pb}_5\text{I}_{16}$ 2D RP perovskite films containing 0 mg/mL (A), 25 mg/mL (B), 50 mg/mL (C) and 75 mg/mL (D) of the cellulose polymer. $\lambda_{\text{exc}} = 400$ nm.

Figure S9. Transient absorption spectra at a delay time of 200 ps of the $\text{BA}_2\text{MA}_4\text{Pb}_5\text{I}_{16}$ 2D RP perovskite films containing 0 mg/mL (black line), 25 mg/mL (green line), 50 mg/mL (orange line) and 75 mg/mL (red line) of the cellulose polymer. $\lambda_{\text{exc}} = 400$ nm.

Table S1. FWHM (cm^{-1}) of the PL peak for the 80-300 K temperature range of the $\text{BA}_2\text{MA}_4\text{Pb}_{5}\text{I}_{16}$ 2D RP perovskite films containing 0 mg/mL and 50 mg/mL of the COS compound.

	Temperature / K											
	80	100	120	140	160	180	200	220	240	260	280	300
0 mg	622	594	535	420	414	515	622	662	704	817	863	928
50 mg	685	656	605	512	473	476	488	518	557	625	676	755

Figure S10. Calculation of the exciton binding energy. a,b) Photoluminescence spectra of the $\text{BA}_2\text{MA}_4\text{Pb}_{5}\text{I}_{16}$ 2D RP perovskite films at different temperatures (80-300 K) containing 10 mg/mL (a) and 75 mg/mL (b) of the COS compound. c,d) $1/\text{Integrated PL intensity}$ as a function of $1/T$ of the $\text{BA}_2\text{MA}_4\text{Pb}_{5}\text{I}_{16}$ 2D RP perovskite films containing 10 mg/mL (c) and 75 mg/mL (d) of the COS compound. The solid lines are best fits using a model that assumes the existence of free and self-trapped excitons.

Figure S11. Photographs of the blended films after three months of exposure to ambient conditions at room temperature.

Figure S12. 2D GIWAXS patterns of the $\text{BA}_2\text{MA}_4\text{Pb}_{51}\text{I}_{16}$ 2D RP perovskite films after two months aged containing different amounts of the COS in the initial precursor solution: 0 mg/mL, 10 mg/mL, 50 mg/mL, and 75 mg/mL.

Figure S13. 2D azimuthal angle patterns of the two months aged $\text{BA}_2\text{MA}_4\text{Pb}_5\text{I}_{16}$ 2D RP perovskite films containing different amount of the cellulose polymer in the initial precursor solution: A) 0 mg/mL, 10 mg/mL, 50 mg/mL and 75 mg/mL.

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